

COATINGS

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Abstract: In this article we will consider the types of coatings

Key words: dental, materials, contact.

Dental materials science differs from mechanical science in that the materials used in relation to a living organism must be absolutely harmless. Then their other properties are determined.

Materials used in dentistry are divided into basic or structural, auxiliary and clinical. The main materials are used in dental orthopedics, they are used to make fillings, dentures and devices. Structural dental materials are divided according to their composition and functions into the following groups:

made of metals and alloys – bridges and crowns;

ceramic – vitals and special porcelain for the manufacture of veneers;

polymer – facing, basic, quick-curing plastics;

sealing and composite – pins and seals.

Auxiliary materials include materials that are used in the manufacture of dentures. Their names depend on the stage at which a particular material is used:

impression – "porridge", used to obtain a sample of the size of the jaws and teeth to which the prostheses are to be fixed;

modeling – they are used to make an exact copy of future prostheses;

shaped – with their help, they prepare the surface of the tooth for prosthetics;

polishing – restore the integrity of the tooth enamel;

insulating – used to separate dentures from healthy teeth.

By composition, additional materials are used in the form of solders, alloys, fluxes and bleaches. The clinical group includes those materials that dentists use at the reception: impression; sealing materials; wax ones.

During work, the dentist uses all materials: basic and auxiliary, but the allocation of clinical materials is important. Special requirements are imposed on materials that have direct and sometimes prolonged contact with the oral cavity. The qualities that dental materials should have: do not contain toxic substances, do not cause allergic reactions and tumor growth in the oral cavity; meet all hygiene requirements – do not create conditions for the deposition of tartar and do not contain on its surface: pits, cracks, hollows, in which food particles may remain; resistance to mechanical stress – the shape of the prosthesis should not change under any

circumstances; have a permanent chemical composition with anticorrosive properties; be plastic during the work, but as hard as possible after its completion.

The application of fluorolac is the coating of enamel with a solution of sodium fluoride or aminofluoride (the composition of the latest generation). As a result, the mineral composition of the enamel is restored and strengthened. The formed film prevents the proliferation of bacteria that cause cavities. Fluorolac prevents the development of carious bacteria on the teeth. In addition to protecting against caries, fluorolac is able to restore the natural mineral structure of teeth, due to the property of fluoride to extract minerals necessary for dental tissues from saliva.

Remineralization is a procedure for restoring the natural structure of tooth enamel by saturating it with minerals. To do this, the teeth are coated with various mineralizing compounds with fluoride and calcium. The remineralization procedure significantly strengthens the enamel, reduces tooth sensitivity and prevents the development of caries.

References:

- 1.I.I. Doynikov, V.D. Sinitsy. Dental materials science. M.."Medicine". 1981.
- 2.M.3. Shteyngart, V.N. Batovsky. Handbook of dental materials science. M., "Medicine", 1981.
- 3.M.V. Bekmetov, F.Sh. Feyzullayev. Orthopedic dental raw materials. T., Publishing house named after Abu Ali ibn Sino, 1994.